

Thracian “Zulmuz-drēnōs” meant “Golden Spear”, and was another name for the Thracian Horse-riding Sun-God/Lightning-God, who was similar to Zeus, Apollo and Dionysus at the same time; Zulmuz= “Golden, flourishing, yellow”, while drēnōs=”spear, wood”, from earlier “hard, firm; tree; wood”; the hill/mountain of Dionysus called Zilmissa by the Thracians was the key to the deciphering

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In a number of Greco-Thracian inscriptions, at least some of which are from a Roman-era shrine of Asclepius located in Thrace (the shrine is known from archaeological remains, a worship center; it is said to date back to the end of the 1st century CE or the beginning of the 2nd century CE), now located near the Bulgarian village of Batkun, Asclepius has an epithet which is attested in a number of variants, including but not limited to: Zulmuzdrīēnos ; Zulmuzdrēn[ōis] (IGBulg 1137), Zulmusdrēnos, Zumzdrēnōs, Zumzdrēnō (IGBulg 1133), Zumudrēnōs.

This epithet, as some previous scholars had pretty much realized, was actually not exactly an epithet of Asclepius, but was instead exactly an epithet of the Thracian Horse-riding Deity, who functioned as the God of Health and Healing among these Thracians; and this god was syncretized with Asclepius in the Greco-Roman era.

This deity was a Sun God as well as the Lightning God/Storm God/Sky God, and indeed some scholars have argued that Zeus was originally a Sun God as well as a Storm God/Lightning God/Sky God, and have argued that the same goes for most if not all Storm God/Lightning God/Sky Gods.

So the Thracian Horse-Riding deity was close to the Greek Zeus, but also to the Greek Apollo, and hence also to the Greek Asklepios. At least once at the shrine of Asclepius near Batkun, Asclepius is depicted as a horseman/horse-rider¹, something not seen in Greece. The votive monuments with images of the Thracian horseman are very fragmented, but it is evident that almost all known iconographic types of the deity are depicted² at the shrine.

The Thracian Horse-Riding deity was also a type of Dionysus god of the springtime and feasting, including drinking wine and such drunken revelry. Among the evidence for that is that Sourogethes, another name for the Thracian horse-riding god, is honored/invoked along with Dionysus at Rosalia festivals (springtime flower festivals and drinking symposiums) in Thrace and Macedonia³.

1 Tsontchev, D. , 1941, *Le sanctuaire thrace près du village de Batkoun*, page 75.

2 Valchev, Ivan (archaeology department at Sofia university), “The Shrine of Asclepius near the village of Batkun”, June 20, 2020; accessed at www.labalkans.org.

3 Kloppenborg and Ascough, *Greco-Roman Associations*, p. 325.

Since Herodotus wrote that the Getae only believe in Salmoxis/Zalmoxis (“believing in other god but their own”, quote from Herodotus Book 4.94) and since Zalmoxis/Salmoxis was most likely ultimately the same as the Thracian horse-riding god (I will detail this later in this work), it makes sense that the Thracian Horse-riding god could encompass so many Greek gods in one deity.

This Thracian Horse-riding deity was usually depicted holding a spear/lance, a spear/lance which was surely equated with both the sun’s rays and lightning bolts/thunderbolts. Like Apollo, this Thracian horse-riding deity was viewed/conceived of as a great Healer of illness and a Bringer and Source of Health and Vigor, Energy and Strength.

So in the inscriptions found near Batkun and elsewhere, the epithets Zulmuzdriēnos ; Zulmuzdrēn[ōis] (IGBulg 1137), Zumzdrēnōs, Zumzdrēnō (IGBulg 1133), Zumudrēnōs (etc.) are epithets of the Thracian horse-riding Sun god/Lightning god/Sky god.

Most of epithet attestations show Zulm- instead of Zum- at the onset of the epithet, and as Peter Delev realized before me⁴, the Zulmuz/Zulmus of some attestations is cognate to and the same as the Zilmis- of the Thracian toponym Zilmissa, despite the different vowels. The toponym Zilmissa is attested in Macrobius, where it referred to a hill or mountain identified with Dionysus, Zeus , Apollo and Sabazios, and where there was a sanctuary to those gods/as well as to the Thracian version of the deity which combined all of those gods, apparently. This Zilmissa is not the same as the shrine of Asclepius in Batkun, but they are both located in what was then Thrace and what is now Bulgaria.

I am the first, it seems, to go on record saying that the Zulm- forms of the epithet are older and thus more etymologically correct than the Zum- forms of the epithet, and I am the first, it seems, to posit that the Proto-Indo-European root of the Zulmuz/Zulmus/Zumulz (etc.) forms and of the Zilm- in Zilmissa is the root *ǵʰelh₃- , “to flourish; green, yellow, golden”. In the toponym, the Zilm- of Zilmissa refers to the golden/yellow Sun, to bright Lightning, and to the green vegetation that arises and flourishes and blooms because of the sun in the sky and the rain from the sky-god/sun-god/storm-god.

The satemization/sibilization of the *ǵʰ sound at the onset of PIE *ǵʰelh₃- to the Z- sound at the onset of Thracian Zulm- is a sound-change that is expected of Thracian, and is seen in a number of PIE languages, including Baltic, Slavic, Phrygian, and Avestan. The Lithuanian word *žalmuo* means “a shoot of corn” and derives from PIE *ǵʰelh₃- “to flourish, bloom; yellow, green, gold”. In Thracian, the element -zelmis at the end of a number of Thracian names has already been posited quite certainly to mean “offshoot, scion, child, offspring” and to derive from PIE *ǵʰelh₃- “to flourish, bloom; yellow, green, gold”.

While the epithet Zulmuzdrēnos (and all its variants) means “Golden Spear”, as I am the first to posit in this paper; and refers to the Spear of the Sun-God/Sky-God/Storm God which was identified with the rays of the sun and with lightning bolts/thunderbolts.

4 See Peter Delev’s paper which in the English version is titled “The Thracian Bessi”, see pages 62 and 64 of the English version of the paper. The reason Delev realized before me that Zulmuz-/Zulmus- of the epithets is cognate to and the same word as the Zilmis- of Zilmissa is because I did not remember the toponym Zilmissa, though very likely in my nearly 20 years of Thracian research, I had seen that toponym before. I am also quite younger than Delev, and presumably he began his Thracian research before I did (I began in the summer of 2004). Note that Delev does not exactly say whether he thinks that the Zulm- forms are older and more etymologically correct than the Zum- forms of the epithet; I am probably the first one to go on record saying that, as I do in this paper.

On page 64 of the English translation, Delev discusses where the hill/mountain Zilmissa was likely located: the exact location is not yet known, but was of course near the Bulgarian village of Batkun.

The *drēnos/driēnos* portion of the epithet meant “spear; wood” (as I am the first to posit), and is cognate Albanian *drënjë*, which means “cornel cherry tree” and also means “strong, healthy, sound”; the cornel cherry tree has very strong wood and the wood of the cornel cherry tree was one of the preferred woods for making spears.

In addition, the semantic shift from “tree, wood” to “spear” is common, and attested as well in Ancient Greek, where *δόρυ* (*doru*) meant “wood, tree” as well as “spear-shaft, spear, lance, pole”.

The cognates of Thracian *drēnos/driēnos* include not only Albanian *drënjë* (variant forms: *drenjë, dreng*), but also Ancient Greek *δóρυ*, Ancient Greek *δρῦς* (“tree, timber, oak/oak tree”), Albanian *dru* (“tree, wood”), Albanian *drinjë* (“brushwood”), Ancient Greek *δρῖός* (“thicket, copse”), Ancient Greek *δρῦμός* (“a thicket, a copse, a wood, a forest”), Ancient Greek *δροόν* (“strong, powerful”), English “tree” and its Germanic cognates, Lithuanian *drutas* (“strong, firm”), as well as many more cognates and possible cognates, including Latin *durus* (“hard, rough”). The Albanian cognate is the closest to the Thracian, both in terms of form and meaning.

Ζάλμοξις (*Zalmoxis*) / *Σάλμοξις* (*Salmoxis*) / *Ζάλμοξεξ* (*Zalmoxes*) (in later manuscripts and later works of the classical era, the form *Samolxis/Zamolxis* is also attested; and in later works, also *Zamolxes, Zamolxe*) is the name of a Getic god who may have been a storm god as well (cf. Herodotus, Book 4.94: “Furthermore, when there is thunder and lightning these same Thracians shoot arrows skyward as a threat to the god, believing in no other god but their own”), and who was said to have risen from the dead like a vegetation god, and who, like *Asclepius*, was identified with a mortal man who was a great healer and sage.

I posit that *Zalmoxis/Salmoxis* also meant “Golden Spear”, and this would explain why, according to Herodotus in Book 4:94 of his *Histories*: “[2] Once every five years they choose one of their people by lot and send him as a messenger to *Salmoxis*, with instructions to report their needs; and this is how they send him: three lances are held by designated men; others seize the messenger to *Salmoxis* by his hands and feet, and swing and toss him up on to the spear-points. [3] If he is killed by the toss, they believe that the god regards them with favor; but if he is not killed, they blame the messenger himself, considering him a bad man, and send another messenger in place of him. It is while the man still lives that they give him the message.”

I analyze the name as a compound comprised of *Zalm/Salm+Oxis/Oxes*; the *Zalm/Salm* portion I posit derives from PIE **ǵʰelh₃-* “to flourish, bloom; yellow, green, gold” like the Thracian *Zulmus-/Zulmuz-/Zilmis-*, and like the Thracian *-zelmis*, and like the Lithuanian word *žalmuo* which means “a shoot of corn”.

The *-οξίς/-οξες* portion I posit is cognate with Ancient Greek *όξύα /όξέα όξύη* which meant “beech tree” and also meant “a spear made of beech wood”. The Armenian cognate *huǵh* (*hac'i*) refers to the ash tree, another tree favored for making spears: in Latin, *frāxinus* (not a cognate) refers to the ash tree and to javelins made of ash tree wood. Likewise for the Latin word *ornus* (also not a cognate), which referred to the mountain ash tree/the rowan tree, and to a lance made of the wood of that tree.

The name of a Getic King, Zalmodegikos, who ruled around 200 B.C., is another Thracian form which shows the form Zalm- at the onset. And since there wasn't a good etymology proposed for Zalmodegikos prior to this paper, I posit, based on another native Albanian word, the word degë ("branch"), that "Zalmo-deg-" meant "Golden Spear"; the suffix -ikos may mean that Zalmodegikos meant "Belonging to Zalmodegis", "Derived/Descended from Zalmodegis" or something like that, since that is the function of the Latin suffix -icus, which is most likely a cognate suffix of the Thracian -ikos.

*Zalmodegis/*Zalmodeges would be an unattested alternative name of Zalmoxis/Salmoxis. For the "branch"~"spear" semantic, see how the English word "javelin" is etymologized as deriving from Proto-Celtic *gablā , "forked branch; fork", as well as other examples one can cite.

Based on our very likely etymologies of Zilmissa, Zulmuzdrenos and of Zalmodegikos, I do not think that the Zalm- of Zalmoxis is the word ζαλμός, a Thracian word that meant "skin; hide of an animal"; this idea is first attested in the work of a Hellenistic Syrian, who recounts how Zalmoxis was said to have been wrapped in a bear's hide at birth. The Thracian word ζαλμός meaning "skin; hide of an animal" would derive most likely from PIE *kel- , "to cover".

And note how the older Zulmu/Zulmuz/Zulmuz became corrupted to Zumu/Zumul/Zumulz/Zumuls in later Thracian; just as Zalmoxis/Salmoxis became corrupted to Zamolxis/Samolxis in later Getic-Thracian. Based on our very likely etymology of Zalmodegikos, as well as our very like etymology of Zulmuzdrenos, I do not think that the -οξίς/-οξες portion of Zalmoxis/Salmoxis is only a suffix, rather I think it is a word that means "spear".

It may be that the other name that Herodotus records for Salmoxis/Zalmoxis, the name Gebeleizis (variant manuscripts have Beleizis/Beleixis, Nebeleizis etc.) also meant "Golden Spear", with Gebel="Golden", and Eizis/Eixis meaning "spear". And it may be that Zibelthiurdos/Zbelthiurdos/Svelsurdos (etc.), another Thracian name for the storm-god/sun-god/sky-god, meant "Shining Spear", with Zibel/Zbel/Svel meaning "Shining/Bright", which poses no problem. And thiurdos/surdos could conceivably have meant "wood, tree; firm, solid", if it was cognate to Proto-Balto-Slavic *twir²tás meaning "hard, firm, solid", from PIE *twerH , a PIE root which is also the source of some Ancient Greek words beginning with s-, as does "surdos", a variant of "thiurdos".

I will investigate these scenarios more in the next edition.

The Ancient Greek playwright Euripides wrote of "Pallas (Athena) of the Golden Lance" in his play Ion, in the opening lines of the play (1:8-9); see: "εστιν γαρ ουκ ασημος ελληνων πολις της χρυσηλογχου παλλαδος κεκλημενη". " χρυσηλογχου παλλαδος" means "Pallas of the Golden Lance/Spear".

Pallas Athena, known primarily as the goddess of battle/war and wisdom, seems to have had many different responsibilities, including a role as goddess of health. Her healing powers were commemorated in a statue in Athens called "Athena Paeconia" (Athena the Healer).

Part 2--- Zeus versus Prometheus, Enlil versus Enki, Thor versus Loki, Veles versus Perkuns; Zalmoxis versus the snake that he is spearing

In the 20th century someone hypothesized that the epithet we have been discussing--- Zalmoxis ; Zalmoxis[ōis] , Zalmoxis, Zalmoxis, Zalmoxis, Zalmoxis, etc.--- means "dragon+water", e.g. "water-dragon", since Asclepius was associated with snakes and with springs of water, and snakes /snake-beings/deities are often associated with springs of water and with rivers and with water in general, both fresh water and salt water.

In a Greek myth, Apollo had to kill Python, a giant snake that made a water-spring go dry, etc., a myth recalling numerous other myths beyond Greece and the Greeks where a dragon must be slain to allow the created universe to arise from the primeval unformed waters guarded by the cosmic Serpent of the Deeps.

Similarly, Cadmus slayed a dragon that "guarded" a water-spring, but the "guarding" apparently involved slaying or potentially slaying anyone who approached too close to the spring; "Cadmus sent some of his companions, Deione and Seriphus, to the nearby Ismenian spring for water. They were slain by the spring's guardian water-dragon which was in turn destroyed by Cadmus, the duty of a culture hero of the new order." Compare also the Hydra of Lake Lerna, the river-god Achelous who could appear as a bull, a snake/giant snake, or a half-man, half-bull; or a giant snake with bulls' horns. The god Oceanus was usually depicted as having the lower body of a serpent attached to a human upper body, human arms and a human head with bulls' horns, though the horns on Oceanus' head were, at least in later times, often replaced with two crabs' arms ending in crab pincers.

In Ancient Italy, at the Etruscan and Roman sanctuary of Bagno Grande—translated as "Great Bath" and located in what is now the Italian province of Siena—some intriguing finds have been unearthed in the hot spring, and they date to classical times; including a series of bronze snakes, including one that measured 35 inches long and was both bearded and horned. It has been classified as an agathodaemon snake (other examples of the same style can be found at the National Archaeological Museum of Naples and the British Museum in London). It would have been seen as the protector of the hot spring.

In the Amazon jungle river-basin, the Quecha people from time immemorial tell of reptilian supernatural water-beings/water-spirits which they call Yacuruna (whose name translates to "water people" in Quechua), who depicted as powerful, enigmatic, and sometimes malevolent spirits that inhabit the depths of the Amazonian rivers and lakes. Many say that those who choose to traverse the remote landscapes of this region, need to always be careful about the Yacuruna. Because those who meet them are often never seen again.

The dualistic nature of the Yacuruna - as both benevolent and malevolent entities - is a recurring theme in Amazonian lore. On one hand, they are believed to possess the power to heal and bestow wisdom. Shamans, or traditional healers, often seek the Yacuruna's guidance during ayahuasca ceremonies, a ritual involving a potent hallucinogenic brew made from local plants. These ceremonies are a profound spiritual journey where the shaman seeks to communicate with the Yacuruna to gain

knowledge, heal ailments, or acquire spiritual power. The Yacuruna are seen as keepers of ancient wisdom and are revered for their deep understanding of the rainforest's medicinal plants and mystical properties.

On the other hand, the Yacuruna are also feared for their ability to abduct humans. Tales abound of individuals being taken to the underwater cities, where they may be kept forever or returned with altered states of mind and body. Those who return often come back as either enlightened healers or profoundly disturbed individuals, hinting at the transformative and perilous nature of their encounters. The Yacuruna's abduction stories serve as cautionary tales, emphasizing the dangers of venturing too close to the water alone or disrespecting the spirits of the river.

From the extremely likely etymology of Zulmuzdrenos that I have uncovered in this paper however, it seems clear that most Thracians at least were not quite dealing with what the Quecha call "Yacuruna", nor with the bearded snake whose bronze effigy was found in that hot spring in Italy. Instead, these Thracians were focusing on and invoking an Apollonian Sun-god/Sky god/Storm-god who like Apollo was a slayer of the serpent, and Zulmuzdrenos slays the serpent with his Golden/Bright Spear.

The "water-snake" theory is from the early era of Thracology (and the works of early Thracology---19th century and 20th century works---are brimming with erroneous interpretations of Thracian material). The original form however was Zulm-, not Zum-⁵, and so there is no linguistic relation to those Slavic words⁶ deriving from Proto-Slavic *zmbjǎ/*zmbjъ="snake; dragon"; which in turn derives (via intermediary forms) ultimately from PIE *d^heg⁻ ("earth") + *-ōm (a suffix); so that Proto-Slavic *zmbjǎ/*zmbjъ="snake; dragon" reflects an original meaning of "animal which lives in/on the ground; earth-creature". For the semantic development within Indo-European, compare the Kamkata-viri words: *babístě*, *bíbímstě* ("snake") < earlier **pa-búm stě* ("being in the ground").

And the second portion of the epithet begins from the D sound (Drēnōs, Driēnōs), not with the Upsilon sound, so there was no actual "udrenos" word intended (a few variants such as Zumudrenos have, by coincidence, the sequence "udrenos", yet more of the variants have "uzdrenos", not "udrenos") and so there is no relation to the Ancient Greek word ὕδωρ "water", deriving from PIE *wódr̥, "water".

I have seen someone theorize that when Heorodotus wrote about the Getae/Thracians shooting arrows at the clouds when thunder/lightning occurred, that may mean that the storm-god/sky-god was an opponent of Zalmoxis, who in that theory is a god like the Slavic Veles, opponent/opposite of Perkuns, the thunder god. I'm very sure that that is not the case. Salmoxis/Zalmoxis was another

5 When some Thracian speakers shifted "Zulmu(s/z)" to "Zumul(s/z)", I think it was simply the ear hearing it wrong, then the mind and tongue saying it wrong. So I don't need to posit that the shift may have been influenced/encouraged by a possible folk etymology where "Zulmuzdrenos" was heard as "Zumul(s/z)drenos" and wrongly interpreted as "Man of Strength/Man of Vigor/Man of Health", if Thracians had a word for "man" that was similar and cognate to Phrygian ζεμελωσ (zemelōs) "man", from PIE *d^heg⁻emelo-, from PIE *d^heg⁻ ("earth") + *-ōm (a suffix). Compare Latin *homō* ("human being, man") and *humus* ("ground, soil"), and similar semantic shift occurring in Semitic languages: Hebrew אָדָם (*adám*, "man"), אֲדָמָה (*adamá*, "soil").

"Drenos" could well have been understood as "Strong, hard, firm", compare Ancient Greek δροόν (droón) "strong, mighty, powerful", from PIE *drew, "tree; hard, firm, strong, solid"; compare how a word for "sick" and "weak" in Latin is *infirmus*, which derives from in- ("not") + firmus ("strong, firm"), from Proto-Italic *en- from Proto-Indo-European *n̥- ("not") + Proto-Italic *fermos from Proto-Indo-European *d^her- ("to hold, support").

6 Besides Slavic words, Romanian zmeu (variant form smeu) means "dragon" and also refers to certain evil giants of Romanian folklore. Most think that the Romanian word derives from Slavic, but the Romanian linguist Sorin Paliga and perhaps others think the Romanian word is from a Non-Slavic and Pre-Roman language of Romania and the Balkans, with the Slavic forms being either cognates or loans from Daco-Thracian. I do not dismiss Paliga's theory; I'm not sure if the Romanian zmeu/smeu is from Slavic: in any case, the Slavic words are at least cognates to the Romanian word, that is for certain.

version of the Thracian Sun-god/sky-god/storm-god who rode a horse and speared a serpent with his Golden/Bright Spear/Lance, while riding his horse.

A note on the linguistic affiliation of Thracian within the Indo-European language of families: the etymologies in this paper once again show that Thracian had much affinity with Ancient Greek, Phrygian, Balto-Slavic and Albanian.

***** Finis of the Second Edition *****